

Creating Employee Performance Through Good Cooperative Governance and Cooperative Management

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ABSTRACT

Cooperatives are jointly owned businesses, not owned by capital holders, so all members have the same voting rights. Apart from that, cooperative members have the same position as the management. The difference is in terms of their authority and duties. Therefore, this research aims to describe and analyze the influence of Good Cooperative Governance and cooperative management on the performance of women's cooperatives in East Java. The design of this research is quantitative causality research. The population in this study were all active cooperative members of the Field Extension Officers (PPL) in East Java. The sampling technique used a simple random sampling technique (random sampling) and used the Slovin formula so that the sample was 172 respondents from women's cooperatives in East Java. Data analysis techniques use descriptive analysis and SEM analysis. This research shows that implementing Good Cooperative Governance and cooperative management has positively impacted the performance activities of women's cooperatives in East Java. Apart from providing education and training, the contribution of cooperative management is to provide more motivation and enthusiasm to be responsible for paying off principal and mandatory savings, one of the cooperative's most significant capital. The management meetings, annual member meetings, and the remaining results of the cooperative's business show that all these criteria have been implemented well to achieve a cooperative with good governance. It is hoped that the results of this research will become a general basis in the world of cooperatives and specifically for women's cooperatives in East Java, East Java as a source for cooperative goals themselves through a model that has been built based on aspects of Good Cooperative Governance and cooperative management in cooperatives.

KEYWORDS: Cooperative Governance, Cooperatives, Performance, Management

1. INTRODUCTION

A cooperative organization will be successful if it is supported by administrators and members who are willing to carry out activities to work together, help each other, provide input and provide maximum service. The positive behavior of management and members in improving cooperative performance depends on managing the motivation or encouragement of members and administrators to carry out their work and obligations (Newman & Ford, 2021).

According to statistical data obtained from the central statistics agency, there are 127,846 active cooperative units in Indonesia in 2021 with a business volume of IDR 182.35 trillion; this number has increased by 0.56 percent compared to the previous year, which amounted to 127,124 active cooperative units. The most significant number of active cooperatives is in East Java, namely 22,845 units,

compared to Central Java, which is in second place with 15,621, and West Java, which is in third place with 10,270 active cooperative units. In East Java alone, active women's cooperatives from 2020 to 2021 amounted to forty-five percent (45%) of the 127,124 active cooperative units (Central Statistics Agency, 2022).

The performance of women's cooperatives in East Java is essential to research because women's cooperatives have a strategic position in strengthening the East Java economy. Women's cooperatives can empower women, grow new micro and small-scale entrepreneurs, prevent urbanization, and create prosperity and security. Apart from that, the performance of women's cooperatives also influences economic growth, employment and financial inclusion in East Java (Wuryani & Yanthi, 2020). By examining the performance of women's cooperatives, the

factors that influence this performance can be identified, as well as the steps that need to be taken to improve the performance of women's cooperatives in the future (Derry & Yvonne, 2021).

Cooperatives are jointly owned businesses, not owned by capital holders, so all members have the same voting rights. Apart from that, cooperative members have the same position as the management. The difference is in their authority and duties (Tortia, 2021). Therefore, it is necessary to study the influence of Good Cooperative Governance and Cooperative Management on cooperative performance through work motivation. The object of research is human resource management, which includes all cooperative members, both administrators and those who are not administrators of Women's Cooperatives in Java. East. So, the performance of the cooperative is limited to the performance of the management and all its members

This research aims to describe and analyze the influence of Good Cooperative Governance and cooperative management on the performance of women's cooperatives in East Java. Theoretical benefits for future researchers: The results of this research can be used as an in-depth study of the field of Human Resource Management and other fields of science. For science development, it is a contribution of thought to advancing expertise in human resource management and other fields of science. Practical Benefits: For cooperatives, the results of this research can be used as a reference or input in improving management and cooperative performance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Gibson's (1997) performance theory, performance is defined as work results related to organizational goals such as quality, efficiency, and other effectiveness criteria. Three variables influence work behavior and performance: individual variables, including abilities and skills, individual background, and demographics. Organizational performance is defined as the organization's effectiveness in meeting the needs of each group through established efforts to improve organizational capabilities sustainably (Barauskaite et al., 2021).

Good Cooperative Governance (GCG), according to Sunaryo (2023), is a set of principles, policies and practices that ensure that cooperatives are run efficiently, transparently, and accountably and comply with applicable laws and ethics. The main goal of Good Cooperative Governance is to create long-term value for cooperative members and other related parties while ensuring that cooperatives operate by considering all stakeholders' interests (Sunaryo et al., 2023).

Peter Davis (1999) formulated that cooperative management is carried out by the people responsible for managing the cooperative, its values and its assets. The people responsible for managing the cooperative use their leadership abilities and choose policies to develop the

cooperative based on the cooperative's professional training results. So, it can be concluded that cooperative management is a professional activity carried out by cooperatives to help all cooperative members achieve their goals.

The definition of cooperative management, according to Kondratyev (2020), is a process that manages the resources owned by the cooperative to achieve organizational goals. The resources in question include human resources, natural resources and financial resources. This process includes planning, directing, organizing, controlling, and testing. Cooperative management is intended to ensure that the resources owned by the cooperative are used efficiently and effectively (Kondratyev et al., 2020). Therefore, the author formulates an initial hypothesis: Good cooperative Governance and cooperative management affect the performance of women's cooperatives in East Java.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

The research was designed according to a quantitative causality research design, namely explaining cause and effect relationships, having a research hypothesis that was then proven using statistical techniques, and explaining an explanation for each variable studied (exploratory research).

3.2 Population and Research Sample

The population in this study were all active women's cooperative members in East Java. The population in this study consisted of members and administrators. Where the administrators were members. However, members only sometimes became administrators of the women's cooperative, with 301 people. The research sample used a random sampling technique, and the sample size was determined using the Slovin formula. In this research, the sample used was composed of cooperative members. In this research, it has a tolerance value of 5%, which means it has an accuracy level of 95%. Thus, the sample was 172 respondents from women's cooperatives in East Java. Sampling in this study used a simple random sampling technique.

3.3 Scope and Location of Research

The scope of this research is human resource management, which is incredibly cooperative management and is linked to the variables of good cooperative governance and cooperative management. This research was conducted at a women's cooperative in East Java. The women's cooperative in East Java was chosen as the research site because this cooperative is unique compared to other women's cooperatives in Indonesia. This cooperative has more than 10,000 members. Another unique thing is that this cooperative is a women's cooperative, which is a consumer cooperative. This cooperative also applies a joint responsibility system and a "One Bring One" (SBS) system,

namely that each member is motivated to bring one person to become a potential new member.

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques

The analysis technique used in this research is the AMOS Structural Equation Model (SEM). SEM AMOS can test theory comprehensively because it integrates path analysis with measurement (confirmatory) analysis.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

Cooperative members perceive Good Cooperative Governance as very appropriate and very good governance for cooperatives because it is a critical aspect that determines the success and sustainability of cooperatives. Good Cooperative Governance includes governance practices ensuring cooperatives run efficiently, transparently and responsibly. The good cooperative governance variable has four indicators, namely transparency (X1.1), accountability (X1.2), responsibility (X1.3), and fairness (X1.4).

The variable indicator for good cooperative governance is accountability (X1.1). The questionnaire item about the cooperative being responsible for all its decisions (X1.1.1) has an average value of 4.220. There were 77 (44.8%) respondents who strongly agreed, 70 (40.7%) respondents agreed, 14 (8.1%) respondents quite agreed, 8 (4.7%) respondents disagreed, and 3 (1.7%) respondents strongly disagreed. This shows that respondents who strongly agree and agree with the statement that cooperatives are responsible for all decisions made are greater than those who agree, disagree and strongly disagree.

The questionnaire item regarding cooperatives is responsible for all business results carried out by members (X1.1.2) with an average value of 4.279. There were 94 (54.7%) respondents strongly agreed, 52 (30.2%) respondents agreed, and 11 (6.4%) respondents somewhat agreed. The value above shows that most respondents strongly agree that the cooperative is responsible for all the business results carried out by its members. However, some respondents still agreed (5.8%), and 5 (2.9%) strongly disagreed. In the questionnaire item regarding Cooperatives implementing a family system in carrying out business activities (X1.1.3), the average value is 4.279. There are 90 (52.3%) respondents strongly agreed with the statement above, 54 (31.4%) respondents agreed, and 17 (9.9%) respondents somewhat agreed. However, there were still respondents who quite agreed, namely 8 (4.7%) respondents and 3 (1.7%) respondents who did not agree with the statement that cooperatives implement a family system in running cooperatives.

Questionnaire item regarding Cooperatives implementing a jointly and severally responsible internal control system efficient (X1.1.4) with an average value of 4.244. There were 89 (51.7%) respondents strongly agree, 52

(30.2%) respondents agreed, 19 (11.0%) respondents quite agreed, while only 8 (4.7%) respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. They agreed with 4 (2.3%) respondents. From value shows that the joint responsibility system controls the best internal tool cooperatives use in cooperative governance. For questionnaire items regarding cooperatives implementing an effective joint responsibility internal control system (X1.1.5), the average value is 4.325. With a value of 97 (56.4%) respondents strongly agree, 50 (29.1%) respondents agree, 12 (7.0%) respondents entirely agree, and 10 (5.8%) respondents disagree, 3 (1.7%) respondents strongly disagree. This matter shows that the respondents believed using the joint responsibility system as an internal control of cooperatives was very important and efficient.

Questionnaire items about cooperatives accountable for all reports finance every month to members (X1.1.6) with an average value of 4.209. There were 86 (50.0%) respondents strongly agreed, 56 (32.6%) agreed, 15 (8.7%) quite agreed, 10 (5.8%) disagreed, and 5 (2.9%) disclosed strongly disagreed. Indicator variable good cooperative governance about transparency (X1.2). Questionnaire items about cooperatives provide complete information about business activities (X1.2.1) and have an average value of 4.482. There are 119 (62.9%) respondents who strongly agree and 30 (17.4%) respondents who agree. This shows that the majority of respondents have the opinion that cooperatives provide complete information about business activities managed by cooperatives. 13 (7.6%) respondents entirely agree, 7 (4.1%) respondents disagree, and only 3 (1.7%) respondents strongly disagree.

The questionnaire item about Cooperatives providing complete information about financial reports to members (X1.2.2) has an average value of 4.244. There were 93 (54.1%) who strongly agreed, 47 (27.3%) respondents said they agreed, 18 (10.5%) said they quite agreed. This shows that most respondents strongly agree that cooperatives provide information about reports finance very complete. Only 9 (5.2%) respondents disagreed, and 5 (2.9%) said they strongly disagreed. Questionnaire items about cooperatives provide complete information about remaining business results to members (X1.2.3) with an average value of 4.133. Most respondents strongly agreed that cooperatives provided complete information about remaining business results.

The questionnaire item regarding the cooperative is responsible for financial management entrusted by members (X1.2.4) with an average value of 4.319. This shows that respondents strongly agree that cooperatives are responsible for managing the finances entrusted by cooperative members. The remaining 7 (4.1%) respondents disagreed, and 3 (1.7%) respondents said they strongly disagreed. Questionnaire items regarding Cooperatives carrying out independent monitoring functions over all aspects (X1.2.5) with an average value of 4.064 and as many as 77 (44.8%) strongly agree, 62 (36.0%) agree, 19 (11.0%) entirely agree, 10 (5.84%) do not agree, 4

(2.3%) strongly disagree. This shows that the majority of respondents agree with the statement that cooperatives carry out an independent monitoring function over all aspects; the rest of the respondents think that they strongly agree, quite agree, and only a tiny number disagree and strongly disagree. The questionnaire item about cooperatives provides the same facilities to members (X1.2.6) with an average value of 4.215. This shows that respondents agree and strongly agree that cooperatives provide the same facility for members.

The indicator of good cooperative governance is responsibility (X1.3). The questionnaire item regarding Cooperatives acting by the cooperative's mission in business activities (X1.3.1) has an average value of 4.168. There were 77 (44.8%). This shows that the majority of respondents stated that they strongly agree that cooperatives act by the cooperative's mission. The second item of the cooperative questionnaire, acting by the cooperative's vision in carrying out business activities (X1.3.2), has an average value of 4.290. The data provides information for most respondents who explained and strongly agree that cooperatives act according to the cooperative's vision in carrying out business activities. The questionnaire item regarding cooperatives complying with the regulations implemented by cooperative legislation (X1.3.3) has an average value of 4.250.

Questionnaire item regarding Cooperatives fulfilling the obligations stipulated by the code of ethics applicable in the cooperative business sector (X1.3.4) average value of 4.162. There were 72 (41.93%) respondents who said they strongly agreed, 71 (41.3%) respondents agreed, and 17 (9.9%) respondents said they quite agreed. This shows that most respondents strongly agree that cooperatives fulfill their obligations set by the code of ethics in the cooperative business sector. Still, 9 (5.2%) respondents disagreed, and 3 (1.7%) strongly disagreed.

The questionnaire item about Cooperatives resolves every problem that fairly occurs within the cooperative. (X1.3.5) has an average value of 4.308. From the data above, most respondents strongly agree that cooperatives resolve every problem that occurs in cooperatives fairly. There are still 4 (2.3%) respondents who disagree and 7 (4.1%) respondents who strongly disagree. Item six: Cooperatives resolve any differences of opinion in a fair manner (X1.3.6) with an average value of 4.162. This shows that most respondents agree that cooperatives finish any differences of opinion in a fair manner. Good variable indicator cooperative The last governance is fairness (X1.4). The questionnaire item about Cooperatives provides equal rights to every member. (X1.4.1) has an average value of 4.174. From the values above, it can be seen that most respondents strongly agree and agree that cooperatives provide equal rights to each member; the remaining few think that they quite agree, disagree and strongly disagree.

Questionnaire items regarding Cooperatives provide the same obligations to each member. (X1.4.2) with an

average value of 4.139. Questionnaire items regarding Cooperatives providing excellent service to members. (X1.4.3) average value 4.267. This shows that the majority of respondents strongly agree with the statement that cooperatives provide excellent service to members. Questionnaire items about Questionnaire Cooperatives maintaining service quality (X1.4.4) have an average value of 4.186. The questionnaire item about the cooperative respecting the rights of each member (X1.4.5) has an average value of 4.191. There were 78 (45.3%) respondents who strongly agreed, 64 (37.2%) respondents agreed, 19 (11.0%) respondents quite agreed, 7 (4.1%) respondents disagreed, and 4 (2, 3%) strongly disagreed. From the values above, it can be seen that the majority of respondents strongly agree and agree with the statement that cooperatives respect the rights of each member; the remaining respondents are very few who agree, disagree and strongly disagree.

The questionnaire item about Cooperatives protecting the rights of each member (X1.4.6) has an average value of 4.197. There were 75 (43.6%) respondents who strongly agreed, 70 (40.7%) respondents said they agreed, and 16 (9.3%) respondents entirely agreed. This shows that the majority of respondents stated that they strongly agree that cooperatives protect the rights of each member. There were 8 (4.7%) respondents who disagreed, and for those who strongly disagreed, there were 3 (1.7%) respondents. The average value of the indicators transparency (X1.1) is 4.243, the average value of the accountability indicator is 4.259, the average value of the responsibility indicator is 4.223, the average value of the fairness indicator is 4.193, and the average value of the good cooperative governance variable is 4.230. Based on the description above, women's cooperatives in East Java have implemented good cooperative governance using a joint responsibility system.

Vari indicator cooperative management capabilities regarding coaching (X2.1). The questionnaire item regarding Cooperatives receiving government facilities in improving the competence of cooperative management (X2.1.1) has an average value of 4.238. There were 82 (47.7%) respondents who strongly agreed, 64 (37.2%) respondents who agreed, and 14 (8.1%) respondents who answered quite agree. This proves that most respondents strongly agree that cooperatives receive facilities and that the government can improve the competence of cooperative administrators. Still, 9 (5.2%) respondents stated they disagreed, and 3 (1.7%) strongly disagreed. The questionnaire item regarding Cooperatives participating in cooperative education programs organized by the government (X2.1.2) has an average value of 4.209. There were 85 (49.4%) respondents who agreed, 58 (33.7%) respondents who agreed, and 13 (7.6%) respondents who entirely agreed. The results provided information that most respondents strongly agree that cooperatives participate in

cooperative education programs organized by the government. Also, 12 (7.0%) respondents disagreed, and 4 (2.3%) strongly disagreed. Questionnaire items regarding cooperatives must adapt to current developments by members' needs. (X2.1.3) with an average value of 4.238. There were 85 (49.4%) respondents who strongly agreed, 59 (34.3%) respondents agreed, and 15 (8.7%) said they quite agreed. These results show that more respondents strongly agree that cooperatives must adapt to current developments and members' needs. However, there were still 10 (5.8%) respondents who disagreed, and 3 (1.7%) respondents didn't agree.

The questionnaire item regarding Cooperatives implementing a cooperative management system by cooperative principles (X2.1.4) has an average value of 4.215. There were 92 (53.5%) respondents strongly agreed, 46 (26.7%) respondents agreed, and 17 (9.9%) respondents somewhat agreed. From the data above, most respondents strongly agree that cooperatives implement a cooperative management system that is in accordance with cooperative principles. However, there was still a small number of respondents who disagreed, 13 (7.6%) and who strongly disagreed, 4 (2.3%) respondents. The questionnaire item regarding Cooperatives conducting regular evaluations (X2.1.5) has an average value of 4.180. There were 85 (49.4%) respondents who strongly agreed with the statement that the cooperative carries out regular evaluations, 53 (30.8%) respondents agreed, and 18 (10.5%) respondents quite agreed. Only a small portion of respondents did not agree with this statement; namely, 12 (7.0%) respondents and 4 (2.3%) strongly disagreed.

The capital variable indicator, with an average value of 4.176, has five questionnaire items, namely the questionnaire item regarding cooperatives having healthy capital to support cooperative business activities (X2.2.1), which has an average value of 4.186. There were 80 (46.9%) respondents who strongly agreed, 60 (34.9%) respondents who agreed, and 19 (11.0%) respondents who somewhat agreed. Proving that respondents predominantly gave answers that strongly agreed with the statement that cooperatives have healthy capital to support cooperative business activities. Apart from that, 10 (5.8%) respondents disagreed, and 3 (1.7%) strongly disagreed. The questionnaire item regarding Cooperatives managing capital efficiently (X2.2.2) with an average value of 4.203. There were 84 (48.8%) respondents strongly agreed, 56 (32.6%) respondents agreed, and 20 (11.6%) respondents somewhat agreed, 7 (4.1%) respondents disagreed, 5 (2.9%)) strongly disagreed. From the data above, it can be seen that most respondents strongly agree, and the second agrees and entirely agrees with the statement that cooperatives manage capital efficiently. However, a few respondents disagreed and strongly agreed with this statement.

The questionnaire item regarding Cooperatives increasing their capital originating from members (X2.2.3) has an average value of 4.203 consisting of 82 (47.7%) respondents strongly agree, 57 (33.1%) respondents agree and 22 (12%) .8%) respondents entirely agree, 8 (4.7%) respondents disagree, and 3 (1.7%) strongly disagree. It can be seen from the data that many respondents strongly agree with the statement that cooperatives increase their capital from members. Followed by respondents who agreed and then those who quite agreed. However, some respondents still disagreed or strongly disagreed with the statements in this third questionnaire. The questionnaire item regarding cooperatives managing capital productively had 86 (50.0%) respondents strongly agree, which indicates that half of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement above. There were 51 (29.7%) respondents who agreed and 21 (12.2%) respondents who agreed that cooperatives managed capital productively. Some respondents disagreed. As many as 10 (5.8%) respondents and 4 (2.3%) strongly disagreed. With an average value of 4.191, respondents agree with the Cooperative statement to manage capital productively.

Questionnaire items about Cooperatives periodically evaluating financial performance showpartThe majority of respondents strongly agreed with 70 (40.7%) respondents, followed by respondents who agreed with 68 (39.5%) respondents, then there were 20 (11.6%) respondents who quite agreed with this fifth questionnaire statement. It has an average value of 4.098, which means that respondents agree with the statement, but there is still a tiny number who disagree or strongly disagree, with 9 (5.2%) and 5 (2.9%) respondents. Education and Training variable indicator (X2.3) with an average value of 4.203. The questionnaire item regarding management often participates in cooperative management education programs organized by cooperatives (X2.3.1) with an average score of 4.279. 87 (50.6%) respondents strongly agreed, which was more than half of the respondents. Only 59 (34.3%) respondents agreed, and 16 (9.3%) agreed. Another 7 (4.1%) respondents disagreed and 3 (1.7%) strongly disagreed with the above statement.

Questionnaire items regarding management often taking part in cooperative management training programs held by cooperatives (X2.3.2) has an average value of 4.157 with 80 (46.5%) respondents strongly agreeing with this statement, 57 (33.1%) respondents agreeing, and 22 (12.8%) entirely agree. A small portion of respondents disagreed with 8 (4.7%) and strongly disagreed with 3 (2.9%) respondents. Questionnaire items regarding cooperative management education helped management improve cooperative operational efficiency (X2.3.3). As many as 85 (49.4%) respondents chose to strongly agree with this statement, 56 (32.6%) agreed and 19 (11.0%)) quite agree. From the data above, the majority say they strongly agree. Only a tiny portion disagreed with 9 (5.2%) respondents, and 3 (1.7%) strongly disagreed, so it had an average value of 4.226.

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Questionnaire items about training management of the participating cooperatives helped the management improve the cooperative's operational effectiveness (X2.3.4), which had an average value of 4.180. 81 (47.1%) respondents strongly agreed with this fourth questionnaire statement, 59 (34.3%) agreed, and 18 (10.5%) somewhat agreed. However, there were still some respondents who disagreed. As many as 10 (5.8%) and 4 (2.3%) respondents strongly disagreed.

The questionnaire items regarding cooperative management education motivated administrators to provide better service to members (X2.3.5). As many as 78 (45.3%) respondents strongly agreed, and this was the majority of respondents. There were 62 (36.0%) respondents who agreed and 20 (11.6%) respondents who quite agreed with questionnaire statement five. Apart from that, there were still 8 (4.7%) respondents who disagreed and 4 (2.3%) respondents who strongly disagreed. In Table 12, it can be seen that the average value of the coaching indicator (X2.1) is 4.216, the average value of the capital indicator (X2.2) is 4.176, and the average value of the education and training indicator (X2.3) is 4.203. Based on the description above, it can be concluded that women's cooperatives in East Java have managed resources and operations or cooperative management to achieve organizational goals effectively. Cooperative performance indicators regarding organizational aspects (Y2.1). Questionnaire items regarding cooperatives' organizational structure effectively determine the function of cooperative positions. The data results showed that 84 (48.8%) respondents responded strongly agree, 58 (33.7%) respondents responded agree, 17 (9.9%) respondents somewhat agreed, 8 (4.7%) respondents disagreed, and 5 (4.7%) respondents, 2.9%) strongly disagreed. The first item of the questionnaire has an average value of 4.209.

The item questionnaire about the organizational structure of an efficient cooperative determines the responsibility of each unit (Y2.1.2), which has an average value of 4.174. The majority chose to strongly agree with 77 (44.8%) respondents, 63 (36.6%) respondents and 20 (11.6%) respondents entirely agree. Not only did the respondents agree, but they also agreed with 9 (5.2%) respondents and 3 (1.7%) respondents strongly disagreed. The questionnaire item regarding the cooperative organizational system is suitable for managing cooperative resources (Y2.1.3). A total of 82 (47.7%) respondents strongly agreed with the statement in the questionnaire, 59 (34.3%) respondents agreed, 17 (9.9%) respondents somewhat agreed, 10 (5.8%) disagreed, and 4 (2.3%) respondents strongly disagreed. This statement has an average value of 4.191, meaning that most agree.

Questionnaire items about cooperative organizational systems are good at integrating cooperative activities (Y2.1.4) with an average value of 4.174 83 (48.3%) respondents strongly agree, 51 (29.7%) respondents agree, and 26 (15.1%) respondents entirely agree. However, 9 (5.2%) respondents disagreed, and 3 (1.7%) strongly

disagreed. Questionnaire items about cooperative organizational culture are consistent with cooperative objectives (Y2.1.5). A total of 82 (47.7%) respondents strongly agreed with a consistent cooperative organizational culture, 53 (30.8%) respondents agreed, and 24 (14.0%) respondents somewhat agreed. A slight majority also chose to disagree, with 10 (5.8%) respondents and 3 (1.7%) respondents strongly disagreeing. This questionnaire has an average value of 4.209.

Questionnaire items about a cooperative organizational culture by cooperative values have an average value of 4.168. The majority of respondents strongly agree with the statement that cooperative organizational culture is based on cooperative values. 82 (47.7%) respondents, 53 (30.8%) respondents agree, 24 (14.0%) respondents entirely agree, 10 (5, 8%) respondents disagree, and 3 (1.7%) respondents strongly disagree with the statement. The next indicator is the management aspect (Y2.2). Questionnaire items regarding the organizational structure carried out by each section in the cooperative are good (Y2.2.1). The majority responded strongly agree, with 84 (48.8%) respondents, 57 (33.1%) respondents agreeing and 20 (11.6%)) respondents entirely agreeing, where this has an average value of 4.226. However, some disagreed with 8 (4.7%) respondents, and 3 (1.7%) strongly disagreed.

Questionnaire items regarding the composition of functions carried out by each section in the cooperative are good (Y2.2.2) with an average value of 4.098. With details, 68 (39.5%) respondents strongly agreed, 70 (40.7%) agreed, 21 (12.2%) respondents somewhat agreed, 9 (5.2%) respondents disagreed, and 4 (2.3%) respondents strongly disagreed. Questionnaire items regarding the results of decision-making in RAT by members' interests (Y2.2.3) have an average value of 4.139. There were 80 (46.5%) respondents who responded that they strongly agreed with the results of decision-making by members' interests, 53 (30.8%) respondents agreed, 26 (15.1%) respondents quite agreed, 9 (5.2%) respondents disagreed, and 4 (2.3%) respondents strongly disagree with the statement.

Questionnaire items regarding the results of decision-making in the RAT are in the interests of the management (Y2.2.4). The majority thought they strongly agreed with the statement, 79 (45.9%) respondents, 59 (34.3%) respondents thought they agreed, and 24 (14.0%) respondents somewhat agreed. A tiny portion still thinks they do not agree with the statement; 7 (4.1%) respondents and 3 (1.7%) respondents strongly disagree. The cooperative management respects questionnaire items regarding each member's rights and the distribution of SHU according to applicable regulations (Y2.2.4). The majority chose to agree, with an average value of 4.174 firmly. 82 (47.6%) respondents strongly agreed, 54 (31.4%) respondents agreed, and 24 (14.0%) respondents somewhat agreed. Whereas some

respondents chose to disagree, with 8 (4.7%) respondents and 4 (2.3%) respondents strongly disagree.

Questionnaire items regarding each distribution of SHU by applicable regulations (Y2.2.6) have an average of 4.162, which means that many respondents agree with the statement and distribution of SHU. With 78 (45.3%) respondents responding strongly agree, 61 (35.5%) respondents agree, and 20 (11.6%) respondents somewhat agree. Several respondents still disagreed with 9 (5.2%) and strongly disagreed with 4 (2.3%). The next indicator is the productivity aspect (Y2.3). Questionnaire items about cooperatives providing quality products according to members' needs (Y2.3.1) with an average value of 4.255, respondents gave positive responses with 90 (52.3%) respondents strongly agreeing, 53 (30.8%) respondents agreeing, and 16 (9.3%) respondents entirely agree. Of the several respondents, there were still negative or disagreeing responses, with 9 (5.2%) respondents and 4 (2.3%) respondents strongly disagreeing.

Questionnaire item regarding cooperatives providing quality services according to members' needs (Y2.3.2). There were 89 (51.7%) respondents who strongly agreed with cooperatives providing quality services, 58 (33.7%) respondents agreed, 14 (8.1%) respondents quite agreed, 8 (4.7%) respondents disagreed, and 3 (1.7%) strongly disagreed. The statements in this questionnaire have an average value of 4.290. The questionnaire item about cooperatives has regular product development innovation (Y2.3.3) with an average value of 4.232. 83 (48.3%) respondents strongly agreed with this statement, 61 (35.5%) respondents agreed, and 16 (9.3%) respondents quite agreed. However, some respondents disagreed with 9 (5.2%) respondents and 3 (1.7%) strongly disagreed.

The questionnaire item about cooperatives has regular service innovation (Y2.3.4) with an average value of 4.215 had 84 (48.8%) respondents who strongly agreed, 60 (34.9%) respondents agreed, 14 (8.1%) respondents quite agreed, 9 (5.2%) respondents disagreed, and 5 (2.9%) respondents strongly disagree. Questionnaire members often get information about products offered by the cooperative (Y2.3.5). 83 (48.3%) respondents responded strongly agreed that members often get information, 59 (34.4%) respondents agreed, and 16 (9.3%) respondents somewhat agreed. The average value of this questionnaire is 4.197. However, some respondents also disagreed with statement with 9 (5.2%) respondents and strongly disagreed with 5 (2.9%) respondents

The questionnaire item states that members often find it easy to access the products offered by the cooperative (Y2.3.6). Positive responses are shown in the data: 93 (54.1%) respondents strongly agree that members often get convenience, 50 (29.1%) respondents agree, and 14 (8.1%) respondents entirely agree. Not only positive responses to this

statement also responded negatively, with 12 (7.0%) respondents disagreeing and 3 (1.7%) respondents strongly disagreeing. Indicators regarding benefit aspects (Y2.4). Questionnaire items regarding products obtained from cooperatives provide benefits according to members' needs, with an average value of 4.162. There are 82 (47.7%) respondents who strongly agree with the statement, 56 (32.6%) respondents agree, 19 (11.0%) respondents entirely agree, 10 (5.8%) respondents disagree, and 5 (2.9%) respondents strongly disagree.

Questionnaire items about services obtained from cooperatives providing benefits by members' expectations (Y2.4.2) have an average value of 4.273. There were 88 (51.2%) respondents who strongly agreed that the services provided were beneficial, 58 (33.7%) respondents agreed, and 14 (8.1%) respondents somewhat agreed. Meanwhile, 9 (5.2%) respondents disagreed and 3 (1.7%) respondents disagreed with the statement. The questionnaire regarding cooperatives provides benefits according to members' needs (Y2.4.3). Many respondents responded that they strongly agreed: 75 (43.6%) respondents, 73 (42.4%) respondents agreed, and 14 (8.1%) respondents somewhat agreed. The remaining 7 (4.1%) respondents disagreed, and 3 (1.7%) strongly disagreed, where this statement has an average value of 4.220.

The questionnaire item regarding products obtained from cooperatives that have added value from cooperatives (Y2.4.4) has an average value of 4.180. 78 (45.3%) respondents strongly agree that the products obtained have added value, 65 (37.8%) respondents agreed, and 16 (9.3%) respondents entirely agree. Notonlyit's still thererespondents8 (4.7%) respondents disagreed, and 5 (2.9%) respondents strongly disagreed. Questionnaire items about product superiority compared to other products (Y2.4.5) with an average value of 4.250, 85 (49.4%) respondents strongly agreed with the statement, 60 (34.9%) respondents agreed, and 15 (8.7%) respondents entirely agreed. Meanwhile, 9 (5.2%) respondents disagreed, and 3 (1.7%) strongly disagreed. Questionnaire items regarding cooperative products positively impact the surrounding environment (Y2.4.6). 79 (45.9%) respondents strongly agreed that cooperative products had a positive impact on the surrounding environment, 60 (34.9%) respondents agreed, and 15 (8.7%) agreed respondents entirely agree, which means that more respondents strongly agree with the statement with an average value of 4.191. Meanwhile, 9 (5.2%) respondents disagreed, and 4 (2.3%) strongly disagreed.

The research results have assessed the good cooperative governance and management that influence women's cooperatives' performance in East Java. The results of testing this hypothesis are as in table 1:

Table 1. Hypothesis Testing Results

No	Exogenous variables	Endogenous variables	Standardized Coefficient	Prob	Results
1	Good Cooperative Governance	Cooperative Performance	0.355	0,000	Significant
2	Cooperation management	Cooperative Performance	0.231	0,000	Significant

Source: Processed Primary Data (2024)

The coefficient value of the influence of the Good Cooperative Governance variable on the performance of women's cooperatives in East Java is 0.355, with a probability value of 0.000, less than 5%. The results show that good cooperative governance significantly impacts cooperative performance. The coefficient value of the effect of cooperative management variables on cooperative performance is 0.231, with a probability value of 0.000, less than 0.05. This shows that cooperative management significantly affects the performance of women's cooperatives in East Java).

4.2 Discussion

Good Cooperative Governance is assessed using accountability, transparency, responsibility and fairness indicators. The superior indicators that reflect good cooperative governance are transparency and accountability. Based on respondents' perceptions, it shows that the most prominent good cooperative governance is transparency or openness and honesty of management in managing cooperatives. Openness and honesty are two essential pillars in building good cooperative governance.

In women's cooperatives in East Java, it is straightforward for members to get information. Openness allows members to access relevant information about the board's operations and decisions, thereby creating a transparent environment. Honesty from every individual, both management and members, ensures that every action and decision is taken based on ethical principles and integrity. With this organized and robust foundation, cooperatives can move towards good cooperative governance, where trust and accountability are the primary keys to collective success. Openness and honesty are not just words but fundamental practices that must be carried out consistently to achieve more significant common goals.

Regarding indicators, cooperative development is an important role carried out by the government in supporting the sustainability of cooperatives based on Law No. 25 of 1992. A questionnaire item states that cooperatives receive government facilities to improve the competence of cooperative management; most respondents agree with this statement.

In cooperatives, women's capital comes from their capital, namely principal savings and members' mandatory savings. The management is an arm of the members

appointed to manage cooperative capital efficiently. One form of efficient capital management is adding businesses in the property sector, businesses in the retail sector, such as SBW Mart and businesses in public health services in the form of SBW clinics. Education and training play an essential role in developing the cooperative movement. Education and training have objectives that include knowledge, skills, and awareness to improve cooperative performance. With the knowledge and skills acquired, members and management can contribute effectively to developing the cooperative. This includes understanding financial management, marketing management, and excellent and correct governance. In cooperatives, women administrators improve cooperative performance by participating in education and training programs on managing cooperatives towards good cooperative governance. Apart from cooperative members, education and training inform the public that cooperatives have essential benefits.

Good Cooperative Governance is based on sound management, transparency, member participation, accountability and justice in cooperative management. Cooperative management also has existing indicators, namely, coaching, capital, education and training. Judging from the research results that have been studied, good cooperative governance and cooperative management significantly affect the performance of women's cooperatives in East Java, which means that by implementing the principles of good cooperative governance and good management, cooperatives can increase operational efficiency. With good cooperative governance, women's cooperatives can empower their members through training, education and other support.

The results of this research have also proven that cooperative management has a significant effect on cooperative performance variables with indicators of guidance, capital, education and training to help cooperative members develop the skills and knowledge needed to contribute optimally to cooperative activities and improve member welfare. The results of this study support research conducted by Candemir et al. (2021) and Muryani et al. (2018); with member involvement in the decision-making process and transparency in management, women's cooperatives can increase the level of member participation. This creates a greater sense of ownership and involvement,

which can increase members' commitment to the cooperative and improve overall performance.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research results and discussions, the implementation of Good Cooperative Governance and cooperative management has proven to positively impact the performance activities of women's cooperatives in East Java. Apart from providing education and training, the contribution of cooperative management is to provide more motivation and enthusiasm to be responsible for paying off principal and mandatory savings, one of the cooperative's most significant capital. The management meetings, annual member meetings, and the remaining results of the cooperative's business show that all these criteria have been implemented well to achieve a cooperative with good governance.

From the descriptions above, the researcher provides suggestions to women's cooperatives to improve the welfare of their members. The cooperative still maintains the joint responsibility system as a system that can fulfill the interests of members by fighting for the welfare of its members. Continue to provide education and training to management and members because, through education and training as well as understanding that continues to be provided to members regarding the repayment of mandatory savings and principal savings, which have a significant influence on the performance of women's cooperatives in East Java, it can foster a sense of ownership and self-development about members. Human resources of women's cooperatives in East Java.

It is hoped that the results of this research will become a general basis in the world of cooperatives and specifically for women's cooperatives in East Java, East Java as a source for cooperative goals themselves through a model that has been built based on aspects of Good Cooperative Governance and cooperative management in cooperatives.

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